

Prevalence and Patterns of Antibacterial Susceptibility During Pregnancy in NSCB Medical College, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh**Shraddha Chandrakar¹, Dipti Markam², Sharad Narayan Sharma³, Ravi Prakash Singh^{4*}**¹Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, NSCB Medical College Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh²Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, NSCB Medical College Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh³Assistant Professor, Department of Anaesthesia, NSCB Medical College, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh⁴ Senior Resident, Department of Paediatrics, NSCB Medical College, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh

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Abstract

Background: Asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) has a comparable prevalence in pregnant women as it does in women who are not pregnant (between 4 and 7 percent). As age, parity, age, and history of asymptomatic urinary tract infection all have a role in the development of ASB, so do lower socio-economic statuses.

Aim and Objectives: This study aimed to (1) determine the incidence of ASB at NSCB Medical College Jabalpur and (2) determine the most common causative microorganisms and their antibiotic susceptibilities.

Materials and Method: From January 2020 to December 2020, 230 healthy pregnant women who had their first prenatal visit at NSCB Medical College Jabalpur were screened for bacteriuria. Antibiotic resistance testing was conducted, and the results were analyzed.

Results: Ten percent of pregnant women had ASB. Except for those living in rural areas ($\chi^2 = 4.454$, $p=0.0348$), demographic and obstetric variables did not substantially affect the prevalence of ASB. *Escherichia coli* was the dominant bacteria (52.17%). Imipenem and aminoglycosides were the most sensitive against uropathogens, while nalidixic acid, ampicillin, amoxicillin, and cotrimoxazole were less sensitive.

Conclusion: Researchers observed that ASB was common among pregnant women. Except for residing in a rural location, neither demographic nor obstetric factors significantly affected the risk of ASB. From what we can see, screening all pregnant women for ASB would be prudent.

Keywords: Pregnancy, Asymptomatic Bacteriuria, Urine Culture, Antibiotic Sensitivity.

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Introduction

Active bacterial growth in the urinary tract, except the distal urethra, in the absence of overt urine symptoms is known as asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB or

asymptomatic substantial bacteriuria). [1] Prevalence rates during pregnancy are comparable to those of the general population. The range is 4%-7%. [2, 3] As

age, parity, age, and history of asymptomatic urinary tract infection all have a role in the development of ASB, so do lower socio-economic statuses. [4, 5]

The isolation of a certain number of bacteria from a urine specimen constitutes the microbiological diagnosis of ASB. Therefore, the gold standard for ASB screening is a urine culture. Studies conducted worldwide and over a wide range of time frames consistently find that *Escherichia coli* is the causative agent in 60–90% of cases of ASB in pregnant women. Other prevalent agents include *Staphylococcus saprophyticus*, Group B beta-hemolytic streptococci, *Enterococcus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Proteus mirabilis*. [6, 7]

Different regions have distinct patterns of frequency and antimicrobial susceptibility among isolated microorganisms. It is important to determine which infections are most prevalent in a given area and to educate the public on the antibiotic susceptibility profiles of these pathogens. Therefore, this study aimed to examine the incidence and risk factors of ASB, the most frequently isolated microorganisms, and the antibacterial susceptibilities of these microorganisms among pregnant women who sought care at a tertiary care facility.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in the Obstetrics and Gynecology and Microbiology Department of NSCB Medical College Jabalpur MP from January 2020 to Dec 2020. Ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee. Informed consent was taken from all participating pregnant women.

Women at any gestational age attending the antenatal clinic for their first visit were included, and those women having a history of urinary tract symptoms (dysuria, frequency, and urgency, etc.), antibiotic administration within the previous seven days, pyrexia of unknown origin and

recurrent UTI were excluded from the study.

The minimal sample size was estimated to be 226 (with 5 percent absolute error at a 95 percent confidence interval and adding 10% attrition rate) considering the prevalence rate of ASB of about 16 percent from the previous study in Northern Indian women. [8] By using systematic sampling method the women were selected. Previous antenatal records showed that an average of 4500 pregnant women visited 1st time in antenatal outpatient departments within a year. This annual number was divided by the minimum sample size ($n=226$) to get a sampling fraction 19.9. Some women may not consent, although it fulfills the inclusion criteria, and therefore sample was taken after the interval of every 15 women though the sampling fraction was 19.

Midstream urine samples were collected for a urinalysis and then cultured using the usual loop method (i.e., 1 ul volume loop) on either CLED (cysteine lactose electrolyte deficient) medium or MacConkey agar and blood agar. The presence of more than 10⁵ CFU/ml of a single organism led to the diagnosis and treatment of ASB in women. [9,10] Antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method, and results were interpreted according to CLSI (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute) guidelines.[11]

A structured proforma was used to obtain data. The data obtained include age, address, educational status, parity, gestational age, history suggestive of urinary tract infection (dysuria, frequency, fever, suprapubic and loin pain), history of antibiotics use, culture, and sensitivity result. Data were presented as numbers and percentages in tables. Chi-square or Fisher's exact tests were used to test for associations. A significant association was presumed if $P < 0.05$.

Results

Of 230 pregnant women tested for ASB, 23 were found to have bacteriuria, for a prevalence of 10%. Age, parity, location, socio-economic position, and gestational age are all factors in ASB, as shown in Table 1.

The maximum rate of 10.40% was found in the 20-30 age group and the minimum rate of 7.69% in the >30 years group. The prevalence relationship among the age group was not statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 0.1488$, $df=2$, $p=0.9283$). Among significant bacteriuria-positive women, the highest prevalence was observed in nulliparous women (11.81%), while women having one or two children had the least prevalence. However, no significant relationship was found between parity and

prevalence ($\chi^2 = 1.038$, $df=2$, $p=0.5950$). Statistically significant ($p=0.011$), ASB was more common among pregnant women who lived in rural areas.

Escherichia coli (52.17%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (21.73%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (17.39%), and *Enterococcus faecalis* (8.69%) were the most common isolates. The antibiotic susceptibilities of the isolates are mentioned in Table 3. *E.coli*, the commonest isolate, was sensitive to cotrimoxazole (41.67% sensitivity) and nalidixic acid (50% sensitivity). Seventy-five percent sensitivity was observed for doxycycline and ciprofloxacin. Sensitivity to nitrofurantoin and gentamicin was 83.33% and sensitivity to cefepime and amikacin was 91.67%. A hundred percent sensitivity was found for imipenem.

Table 1: Prevalence of ASB among pregnant women

Variables	Significant bacteriuria	No significant bacteriuria	Total number of cases
Age in years			
<20	4 (9.9)	40 (90)	44
20-30	18 (10)	155 (89)	173
>30	1 (7.69)	12 (92.31)	13
Parity			
0	15 (11)	112 (88)	127
1-2	7 (7.69)	84 (92.31)	91
>3	1 (8.33)	11 (91.67)	12
Locality			
Rural	21 (13)	140 (86)	161
Urban	2 (2.89)	67 (97)	69
Literacy			
Illiterate	3 (9.9)	30 (90.9)	33
Primary	10 (10.64)	84 (89.3)	94
High school	8 (10.39)	69 (89.6)	77
Higher education	2 (7.69)	24 (92.31)	26
Gestational age			
1 st trimester	3 (8.11)	34 (91.89)	37
2 nd trimester	9 (10.98)	73 (89.02)	82
3 rd trimester	11 (9.91)	100 (90.09)	11

Data are expressed as a number of patients (percentage)

Table 2: Bacterial isolates among pregnant women with significant bacteriuria

Bacterial isolates	Number of women with isolates	Percentage
Escherichia coli	12	52.17
Staphylococcus aureus	4	17.39
Enterococcus faecalis	2	8.69
Klebsiella pneumoniae	5	21.73
Total	23	100

Klebsiella pneumoniae, the second most frequent isolate, was 60% sensitive to nalidixic acid, ampicillin, and cotrimoxazole. Sensitivity to amoxicillin,

ciprofloxacin, nitrofurantoin, and doxycyclin was 80%, and that for cefepime, amikacin, gentamicin, tobramycin, and imipenem was 100%.

Table 3: Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern

Drugs	E. Coli	S. aureus	E. faecalis	Klebsiella
Ciprofloxacin	9 (75)	4 (100)	0 (0)	4 (80)
Nitrofurantoin	10 (83.33)	ND	1 (50)	4 (80)
Nalidixic acid	6 (50)	ND	ND	3 (60)
Cefepime	11 (91.67)	3 (75)	ND	5 (100)
Amikacin	11 (91.67)	3 (75)	2 (100)	5 (100)
Ampicillin	7 (58.33)	ND	1 (50)	3 (60)
Amoxicillin	8 (66.67)	2 (50)	2 (100)	4 (80)
Cotrimoxazole	7 (41.67)	3 (75)	1 (50)	3 (60)
Doxycyclin	9 (75)	2 (50)	2 (100)	4 (80)
Azithromycin	ND	4 (100)	2 (100)	ND
Gentamicin	10 (83.33)	ND	2 (100)	5 (100)
Tobramycin	ND	ND	ND	5 (100)
Vancomycin	ND	4 (100)	2 (100)	ND
Imipenem	12 (100)	4 (100)	ND	5 (100)

Data are expressed as a number of patients (percentage), ND: not done.

All the Staphylococcus aureus isolates were sensitive to ciprofloxacin, azithromycin, vancomycin, and imipenem; two (50%) were sensitive to amoxicillin and doxycycline, and three (75%) were susceptible to cefepime, amikacin, and cotrimoxazole. All isolates of Enterococcus faecalis were sensitive to amoxicillin, amikacin, doxycycline, gentamicin, azithromycin, and vancomycin; no one was sensitive to ciprofloxacin, one to ampicillin, nitrofurantoin, and cotrimoxazole.

Discussion

The prevalence of ASB among pregnant women was 10% in this study, close to

9.5% reported in the study from Kumasi, Ghana[12]. The incidence is less than the 13.5% reported in Mangalore, Karnataka [13], 17% in Nellore [14], and 26% in Chitwan, Nepal [15]. This exceeds the 7.3% found in the Kanpur, India study. [16]

The highest prevalence, 10.40%, was recorded in the 20-30 age group, while the lowest prevalence, 7.69%, was documented in the >30 age group. There was no significant age-related difference in the prevalence of ASB ($P = 0.6597$). In a study by Imade PE et al. [17], 1228 pregnant women were evaluated, and maximum prevalence was observed between the 20-30

years age group, comparable to the present study. In a study performed in Ghana, 220 pregnant women were examined, and the prevalence of ASB was reported maximum in the age group of >35 years, which contrasts with our findings. [18]

Concerning parity, nulliparous women had a prevalence of 11.81% as against 7.69% in the parity of 1 or 2. The parity distribution in this study did not significantly affect ASB. Similar studies have been reported in Nigeria[19] and Ghana¹². This was in contrast to previous research that found that ASB during pregnancy was linked to having more children. [20, 21]

Findings from the study reveal that the prevalence of ASB who resided in rural areas was significantly higher than in urban areas ($\chi^2 = 4.454$, $df=1$, $p=0.0348$). A similar finding was observed in the study of Onu FA et al. [22]

Using educational status as a parameter of socio-economic status, no significant association was found between asymptomatic bacteriuria and educational status. This finding was comparable with the study of Labi et al.[23] However; the finding was at variance with the observations from southeastern Nigeria, where ASB mainly was seen among the least educated women.[24]

Consistent with what was found by Nath et al., ASB was more common in the second trimester of pregnancy.[25] The study found that *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* were the most common types of bacteria. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Enterococcus faecalis* were the other microbes found. Umamageswari[26], Chandel [27], and Gayathree [28] all found results consistent with this hypothesis.

The maximum sensitivity to different antibiotics exhibited by uropathogenic in this study was as follows: *E. coli* – 100% sensitive to imipenem; *S. aureus* – 100% sensitive to imipenem, vancomycin, azithromycin, and ciprofloxacin; *K.*

pneumoniae – 100% sensitive to imipenem, tobramycin, gentamicin, amikacin, and cefepime; *E. faecalis* – 100% susceptible to vancomycin, azithromycin, gentamicin, doxycycline, amikacin, and amoxicillin. The uropathogenic were least sensitive to nalidixic acid, ampicillin, amoxicillin, and cotrimoxazole. The reason behind resistance to these may be self-medication, antibiotic abuse, low cost, and availability of drugs. Even though antibiotics' sensitivity and resistance pattern varies from community to community and hospital to hospital due to indiscriminate use, our study is consistent with other studies[16]. showing that different uropathogens remain highly sensitive to imipenem and aminoglycosides.

Conclusion

Women who were pregnant and had ASB were 10% of the study population. There was no significant difference in the prevalence of asymptomatic bacteriuria between urban and rural dwellers. Most infections are caused by *E. coli*, which can be treated with aminoglycosides and imipenem. Educating doctors on antibiotic use and avoiding providing empirical therapy is crucial in light of the evolving patterns of bacterial resistance to commonly used medicines.

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